

Reduction of gold(III) by malonate in acetate buffer : Mechanism of the rate processes

Pratik K. Sen^{*a}, Anirban Sarkar^a, Krishnendu Maiti^a and Biswajit Pal^{*b}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Jadavpur University, Kolkata-700 032, India

E-mail : senpk@yahoo.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, St. Paul's Cathedral Mission College, 33/1, Raja Rammohan Roy Sarani, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : palbiswajit@yahoo.com

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Abstract : The kinetics of reduction of tetrachloroaurate(III) by sodium malonate has been spectrophotometrically studied in acetic acid-sodium acetate buffer in the pH range 4.20–4.83. The reaction is of first order with respect to Au^{III} but of complex order with respect to substrate and H⁺. The rate of reaction increases with increasing ionic strength and increasing [H⁺]. The rate is also enhanced with an increase in the dielectric constant of the medium. AuCl₃(OH)⁻ and malonate anion are presumed to be the predominant reactant species under experimental conditions. AuCl₃(OH)⁻ reacts with malonate ion to produce an intermediate species which in turn decomposes in the rate determining step to yield glycolic acid, CO₂ and Au^I. Thermodynamic parameters associated with different reaction steps have been evaluated.

Keywords : Reduction, sodium malonate, tetrachloroaurate(III), acetate buffer, kinetics and mechanism.

Introduction

Malonic acid is an important chemical which is widely used in medicine and in various chemical industries. While it is used in its ester form in the pharmaceutical industry, its pure form is highly reactive and unsafe. Malonic acid and its esters are characterized by the large number of condensation products. They are important intermediates in syntheses of vitamins, barbiturates and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs¹. The kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of malonic acid has been studied by different oxidants such as Cr^{VI}², Mn^{VII}³, Mn^{IV}³, Mn^{II}-catalysed bromate⁴ and Bi^V⁵. The biological importance of gold(III) compounds have been reported⁶⁻⁹. The kinetics of oxidation of a few alcohols¹⁰, glycolaldehyde¹¹, α -hydroxyacids¹² and oxalic acid¹³ by Au^{III} have already been reported. An attempt has therefore been made to investigate the mechanism of oxidation of malonic acid, another dicarboxylic acid, by tetrachloroaurate(III). It will also be interesting to find out whether Au^{III} is reduced by a single two-electron transfer step, or two, one-electron transfer steps¹⁴.

Experimental

Reagents :

All the reagents were of analytical grades. Sodium malonate was prepared by neutralising 0.8 mol dm⁻³ malonic acid (extra pure AR, SRL, India) by 0.8 mol dm⁻³ sodium hydroxide. Au^{III} solution was prepared by dissolving approximately 1 g of chloroauric acid (AR, SRL, India) in 50 mL of 0.01 mol dm⁻³ HCl solution. The strength of this solution was determined by measurement of the absorbance of the solutions (after proper dilution in 0.01 mol dm⁻³ HCl and 1 mol dm⁻³ NaCl) at the absorbance maximum (313 nm)¹³ of AuCl₄⁻. All the solutions were made in doubly distilled water.

Kinetic measurements :

The kinetics of the reaction was studied under pseudo-first order condition where [malonate] \gg [Au^{III}], i.e. the substrate concentration was taken in large excess compared to the oxidant concentration. The course of the reaction was studied spectrophotometrically by measuring the absorbance of the mixture at 400 nm at known intervals of time. All the kinetic investigations were carried

out in an Elico (India) UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Model BL-198) with a peltier controlled thermostated cell compartment. At least 20 experimental readings were taken for each set of experiment. The plots of $\ln A$ (A = Absorbance at time t) versus time (Fig. 1) were linear and the pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were determined from the slope of the straight line in each case.

Fig. 1. Pseudo-first order plots at different malonate concentrations. Plot of $\ln A$ versus 'time' at 311 K : $[\text{Au}^{\text{III}}] = 1.114 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{H}^+] = 3.47 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{Cl}^-] = 0.01 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{Malonate}] =$ (a) $1.6 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; (b) $3.2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; (c) $5.6 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; (d) $8.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; (e) $12.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; (f) $16.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Product analysis :

The reaction mixture (concentration of each reactant being twenty times that under the kinetic condition) was allowed to stand for 3 h and then distilled, the distillate being collected in a closed container. About 2 mL of the distillate was mixed with a little amount of chromotropic acid and 2 mL of 12 N sulphuric acid and warmed on a water bath for about 5 min when a pinkish violet colour appeared indicating the presence of glycolic acid¹⁵. Since malonate was in large excess, the possibility of further oxidation of glycolic acid was very small, although it cannot be totally ruled out. Hence, the reaction follows the stoichiometry,

Polymerization test :

2.5 mL buffer (pH = 4.5), 1.0 mL of 0.4 mol dm^{-3}

sodium malonate, 0.2 mL of 0.25 mol dm^{-3} NaCl solution and 1.0 mL acrylonitrile were mixed together and finally 0.1 mL of 0.22 mol dm^{-3} Au^{III} solution was added to it. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for almost 1 h. No polymerization of acrylonitrile was observed. This showed that there was no free radical intermediate, thus indicating the absence of one-electron transfer process¹⁶⁻¹⁸ in the reduction of $\text{Au}^{\text{III}}\text{-Au}^{\text{I}}$.

Results and discussion

The reaction course was monitored by following the decrease in concentration of Au^{III} . The plot of $\ln A$ vs time (t) was found to be linear (Fig. 1) indicating that the reaction was first-order with respect to Au^{III} . The rate of the reaction was studied at different temperatures at different malonate concentrations ($(1.6\text{--}16) \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) keeping $[\text{Au}^{\text{III}}]$, $[\text{Cl}^-]$ and $[\text{H}^+]$ constant at $1.114 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, 0.01 mol dm^{-3} and $3.47 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ respectively. The rate of the reaction at each temperature increased with increase in $[\text{malonate}]$ (Table 1). The plot of k_{obs} versus $[\text{malonate}]$ at each temperature did not produce straight line passing through the origin, instead a plot of k_{obs}^{-1} versus $[\text{malonate}]^{-1}$ at each temperature produced a straight line with a positive slope and a positive intercept (Fig. 2). Thus a Lineweaver and Burk type plot indicates the formation of an intermediate complex between Au^{III} and the substrate preceding the rate determining step.

The reaction was studied at 306 K at different ionic strengths varied by the addition of NaClO_4 $[(0\text{--}0.48) \text{ mol dm}^{-3}]$ but at constant $[\text{Au}^{\text{III}}]$, $[\text{malonate}]$, $[\text{Cl}^-]$ and $[\text{H}^+]$ of $1.114 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, 0.08 mol dm^{-3} , 0.01 mol dm^{-3} and $3.47 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ respectively. The rate was

Table 1. Variation of pseudo-first order rate constant with malonate concentration at different temperatures

$[\text{Au}^{\text{III}}] = 1.114 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}^+] = 3.47 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Cl}^-] = 0.01 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

10^2 [Malonate] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)			
	296 K	301 K	306 K	311 K
1.6	1.06	1.82	2.33	3.13
3.2	1.69	2.95	3.69	4.92
5.6	2.37	4.10	5.12	6.87
8.0	2.90	5.05	6.30	8.41
12.0	3.56	5.88	7.80	9.99
16.0	3.97	6.53	8.55	11.50

Fig. 2. Effect of malonate concentrations on the reaction rate at different temperatures. Plot of k_{obs}^{-1} versus $[\text{Malonate}]^{-1}$ at different temperatures : $[\text{Au}^{\text{III}}] = 1.114 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{H}^+] = 3.47 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{Cl}^-] = 0.01 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

found to increase with an increase in ionic strength. A plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $\mu^{1/2}$ was found to be linear (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Effect of ionic strength on the rate constant. Plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $\mu^{1/2}$ at 306 K : $[\text{Au}^{\text{III}}] = 1.114 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{Malonate}] = 0.08 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{Cl}^-] = 0.01 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{H}^+] = 3.47 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

The rate of the reaction was studied in the temperature range (296–311 K) at different $[\text{H}^+]$ ($(1.48\text{--}6.17) \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) using sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer, while keeping $[\text{Au}^{\text{III}}]$, $[\text{malonate}]$ and $[\text{Cl}^-]$ constant at $1.114 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, 0.08 mol dm^{-3} and 0.01 mol dm^{-3} respectively. The ionic strength was maintained constant by the addition of sodium perchlorate. The rate constants were found to increase with an increase in $[\text{H}^+]$. A plot of

k_{obs}^{-1} versus $[\text{H}^+]^{-1}$ was found to be linear at each temperature (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Effect of $[\text{H}^+]$ on the rate constant. Plot of k_{obs}^{-1} versus $[\text{H}^+]^{-1}$ at different temperatures : $[\text{Au}^{\text{III}}] = 1.114 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{Malonate}] = 0.08 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{Cl}^-] = 0.01 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

The effect of solvent polarity on the rate of the reaction was studied by the addition of 1,4-dioxane (0–24% v/v) while keeping $[\text{Au}^{\text{III}}]$, $[\text{malonate}]$ and $[\text{Cl}^-]$ constant at 306 K. The rate constant was found to decrease with decreasing dielectric constant of the medium (Table 2).

Table 2. Variation of pseudo-first order rate constant with change in dielectric constant of the medium at 306 K

$[\text{Au}^{\text{III}}] = 1.114 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Malonate}] = 0.08 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Cl}^-] = 0.01 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}^+] = 3.47 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

% 1,4-Dioxane (v/v)	ϵ	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s^{-1})
0.00	59.34	6.36
4.0	58.10	6.31
10.0	56.24	6.05
16.0	54.50	5.74
24.0	52.20	5.68

In a dilute solution of tetrachloroauric(III) acid, the following equilibria are known to exist^{19,20} :

where, the different 'K' values are the equilibrium constants of the respective steps at 298 K. Thus four different species, viz. HAuCl_4 , AuCl_4^- , $\text{AuCl}_3(\text{OH}_2)$ and $\text{AuCl}_3(\text{OH})^-$ may act as oxidants in the present reaction. However, most of the experiments were carried out in a solution of $[\text{H}^+] = 3.47 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $[\text{Cl}^-] = 0.01 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. Under such experimental condition, $[\text{AuCl}_4^-] : [\text{HAuCl}_4] = 2.88 \times 10^4 : 1$ which indicates that $[\text{HAuCl}_4]$ is negligible in comparison to $[\text{AuCl}_4^-]$. Again from equilibrium (3), it is found that $[\text{AuCl}_3(\text{OH}_2)] : [\text{AuCl}_4^-] = 1 : 1053$. Hence the contribution of $[\text{AuCl}_3(\text{OH}_2)]$ may also be neglected compared to $[\text{AuCl}_4^-]$. Of the remaining two species, the values of K_2 and K_3 suggest that $[\text{AuCl}_3(\text{OH})^-] : [\text{AuCl}_4^-] = 7.5 : 1$. Moreover, it has been shown by earlier studies^{10,13} that $\text{AuCl}_3(\text{OH})^-$ is 5–20 times more reactive than AuCl_4^- . Therefore, it has been assumed that $\text{AuCl}_3(\text{OH})^-$ is the main oxidising species of Au^{III} in the present reaction.

The first dissociation²¹ of malonic acid may be represented as :

where, $K_4 = 1.4 \times 10^{-3}$ at 298 K. From this known value of K_4 and at $[\text{H}^+] = 3.47 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, the ratio $[\text{A}^-] : [\text{HA}] = 40 : 1$. Thus the reductant remains mostly in the form of malonate anion, A^- ($\text{HOOC} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{COO}^-$). Therefore, the reaction possibly takes place between $\text{AuCl}_3(\text{OH})^-$ and $\text{HOOC} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{COO}^-$.

The reaction has been found to be accelerated by H^+ ions. Also a linear double reciprocal plot of k_{obs}^{-1} versus $[\text{malonate}]^{-1}$ suggests a pre-equilibrium involving the formation of an intermediate complex (X) between the oxidant and the substrate followed by the decomposition of the complex in the rate determining step. Such type of intermediate complex has been reported¹² in the oxidation of some α -hydroxyacids by Au^{III} . Also the reaction failed to induce polymerization of acrylonitrile indicating that possibly Au^{III} here acted as a two electron transfer oxidant. Based on the above facts, the following scheme of

reaction may be suggested.

Scheme 1

The decomposition of the intermediate complex (X) in the rate determining step may be thought to occur as follows :

Scheme 2

According to the suggested scheme, the rate of the reaction becomes

$$V = - \frac{d[\text{Au}^{\text{III}}]}{dt} = \frac{k_d K_5 [\text{Au}^{\text{III}}] [\text{H}^+] [\text{S}]}{1 + K_5 [\text{H}^+] [\text{S}]} \quad (6)$$

where, 'S' stands for malonate.

Thus the pseudo-first order rate constant (k_{obs}) may be obtained as

$$- \frac{1}{[\text{Au}^{\text{III}}]} \frac{d[\text{Au}^{\text{III}}]}{dt} = k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_d K_5 [\text{H}^+] [\text{S}]}{1 + K_5 [\text{H}^+] [\text{S}]} \quad (7)$$

The eq. (7) may be rearranged as,

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{k_d} + \frac{1}{k_d K_5 [\text{H}^+] [\text{S}]} \quad (8)$$

Thus a plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/[\text{malonate}]$ should be a straight line having a positive slope and positive intercept on the Y-axis and this has been corroborated by the experimental results (Fig. 2). From the intercept and the slope of the linear plots, the values of k_d (disproportionation constant, Scheme 1) and K_5 (equilibrium constant for the formation of intermediate complex, Scheme 1) were determined at each temperature. Both the values of

Table 3. Values of disproportionation constants and thermodynamic parameters both from substrate and acid effects

Experiment	$10^4 k_d$ (s ⁻¹)				Thermodynamic parameter			
	296 K	301 K	306 K	311 K	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH^0 (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^0 (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
Substrate effect	5.28	8.86	11.30	14.78	48.62	-31.0	3.03	118.41
Acid effect	5.31	9.11	10.97	14.29	45.89	-40.08	3.67	123.14

Fig. 5. Effect of temperature on the disproportionation constant. Plot of $\ln(k_d/T)$ versus $1/T$.

k_d and K_5 were found to increase with increase in temperature. The enthalpy of activation (ΔH^\ddagger) and the entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) for the rate determining step (Scheme 1) were evaluated from the linear plot of $\ln(k_d/T)$ versus T^{-1} (Fig. 5) using Eyring equation. Also the thermodynamic parameters (ΔH^0 and ΔS^0) for the equilibrium step (Scheme 1) were calculated from the linear plot of $\ln K_5$ versus T^{-1} . The values of activation and thermodynamic parameters are presented in Table 3.

Eq. (8) also suggests a linear plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/[H^+]$, which was actually obtained experimentally (Fig. 4) at each temperature. The values of k_d and K_5 were also evaluated from these plots. The values of k_d obtained from substrate effect as well as acid effect have been compared (Table 3). The increase in rate with an increase in ionic strength may be accounted for by the fact that in the rate determining step, the intermediate complex breaks down into several charged species, which indicates that the transition state is much more polar which will be favoured by higher ionic strength of the medium and this explains the increase in rate with an increase in ionic strength. Also a transition state with a greater polarity than the initial state will be favoured by high dielectric constant of the me-

dium. The decrease in rate with increase in proportion of 1,4-dioxane is thus explained. Since the transition state will be much more polar than the intermediate complex (X), there will be a greater amount of electrostriction²² (i.e. more solvent molecules will get bound to the transition state than the reactant, X) which should result in a negative entropy of activation, a fact that has actually been observed. Thus all the kinetic evidences as well as thermodynamic parameters and the absence of polymerization justify the proposed mechanism in which Au^{III} oxidizes malonate ion in a one-step two electron transfer process.

Conclusion

Reduction of Au^{III} by malonate in acetate buffer medium takes place through a two electron transfer step. Of the four species of gold(III), predominantly $\text{AuCl}_3(\text{OH})^-$ reacts with malonate ion to produce glycolic acid, CO_2 and Au^I. Disproportionation constant values at different temperatures obtained from substrate effect corroborate with those calculated from pH effect which justify the derived rate law.

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